

Original Article

Alleviating Poverty in Pakistan: Insights from China's Success Story

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Abstract

This work is a comparative study of poverty mitigation policies of China and Pakistan with particular reference to CPEC. China had similar levels of poverty to Pakistan in the late 1970s, but the country has made huge progress in fighting poverty, while Pakistan has struggled. Factors that contributed to China's success have been examined in the following paper including institutions reform, macro stability, anti-poverty measures (part of broader poverty reduction strategies). In comparison, Pakistan has been lagging behind because of the weak institutional capacity, paternalistic mode of governance, and issues with being able to effectively run poverty alleviation initiatives. The study further discusses the CPEC enlightenment about Sustainable development in Pakistan and demands balanced and fair policies to handle the environmental and social impacts. The purpose of this paper drawing lessons from China, is to inform policy decisions that can assist Pakistan in achieving its poverty reduction targets.

Keywords: China Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC), Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), Special Economic Zones (SEZs)

Introduction

Pakistan continues to be a country afflicted by impoverishment, with millions of individuals lacking access to vital supplies such as food, education, and healthcare. Despite attempts to address poverty, the country still struggles with slow and uneven progress. Whereas, China over the past few decades has achieved incredible success in that regard by lifting hundreds of millions of people out of extreme poverty. The purpose of this paper is to highlight how China has achieved success in term of poverty alleviation and which lessons can be learned by Pakistan from the Chinese experience.

To analyze the methods and techniques for poverty reduction used by China and Pakistan, including the importance of economic growth, social protection programs, and institutional factors the comparative analysis framework will be used. Furthermore, the study will explore the impact of China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) on poverty reduction in Pakistan, particularly in relation to the China Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC). An examination of poverty alleviation initiatives in China reveals that a mix of strong economic growth, alongside specific social protection programs and industrial reforms, has influenced China's strategy for reducing poverty (Arif & Farooq, 2012).

The economic liberalization in China that began in the late 1970s has been vital in raising millions above the poverty line, particularly in rural areas (Jenkins & Edwards, 2004). Conversely, the alleviation of poverty in Pakistan is limited by various issues that include corruption, in-stable governance and politics, and inadequate institutional capacity (Ashraf, 2017).

The study will also explore the effects of CPEC on poverty alleviation in Pakistan, emphasizing the possible advantages and obstacles of this project. This paper seeks to offer policy recommendations for enhancing alleviation strategies in Pakistan by examining the insights that can be gained from China's experiences.

Literature Review

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The problem of poverty has always constituted a focus point in development debates especially in the Post Washington Consensus countries that are cyclically challenged by issues of inequality, governance and institutional framework. The cases of Pakistan and China demonstrate two stories that provide a best, proper yet different view on how reforms, education, infrastructure, governance as well as and access to financing intersect in relation to poverty.

Comparative Foundations of Poverty Alleviation

(Arif & Farooq, 2012) provide the preliminary comparative framework of Pakistani and Chinese poverty paths from the 1970s. At the time when South and North of the Red River were equally impoverished, China embarked on the rural reform that would later become a great beginning, where the Household Responsibility System (HRS) was used as a strategy. The land reform program, subsidies for farming, and resultant gains in productivity helped millions of peasants to abandon poverty while state development of education, construction of new universities, and improvements in the delivery of health care followed faithfully. Even though they positively affected livelihoods they also sparked more macroeconomic stability and inclusion. On the same note, Pakistan has made some little progress in poverty reduction due to weaknesses in institutional capacity, fluctuating land reforms and poor attention to the development of the agricultural sector in Pakistan. Writing of (Arif & Farooq, 2012). Contains governance deficits that have seen Pakistan to lag behind in coming up with proactive solutions to poverty control in view of inequality in the country especially for the rural poor. The series also highlight important lessons in political leadership and governance, institutional changes, and especially political will in the poverty mix.

Education and Infrastructure: The Pillars of Economic Mobility

In their recent study, (Ullah et al.2020) concerned with educational functions in poverty eradication associate education with the process of socio-economic development as an antecedent, as well as its result. They claim that projects of China Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) are useful in developing a mechanism to fill the gap of educational development as well as Infrastructure advancement in Pakistan. CPEC projects break barriers such as rural-urban transport facilities and transaction cost, provide ladder to poor and marginalized people to come in the mainstream and get in better position to avail better opportunities in education and employment. Building upon this the present study by (Muzammil Zia et al., 2018) elaborates this discourse with relation to SEZs under CPEC as agents of change. Based on the successful experiences of the SEZs of China they have proposed the framework of localized governance system, skill development and labor protection policy to harness the full fruits of the SEZs. But they also discuss the problems faced by Pakistan with regards to the proper implementation of SEZs including infrastructural constraints, governance issues, and lack of proper stakeholder interaction. It is therefore important to point out that this work underlines the necessity and emphasis on a strategic approach in SEZs development so as to ensure that SEZs are consistent with national development plan and priorities thus achieving desirable development impact across the regions.

Global Perspectives on Trade, FDI, and Poverty

There is a kind of a global outlook derived from analyzing Chinese impact on poverty reduction in other world countries, provided by (Jenkins and Edwards, 2004). Their study identifies trade and FDI as double-edged swords: as they generate employment opportunities for countries that depend on labor-intensive industries, they on the same note increase inequality if dealt with averagely. The authors highlight the use of profits alongside social and environmental objectives, especially in sectors that impact poverty leverage depending on employment standards. Talking about consequential socio-economic effects of CPEC, (Menhas et al. 2019) use Pakistan's social needs in energy, employment situation and infrastructural disequilibrium as endogenous variables. They explain how CPEC energy projects including the solar and wind ventures play a pivotal role in extending energy that is central to industrialist intentions plus poverty eradication. But they warn that Chinese funding poses dangers of excessive borrowing and environmental pollution, and the displacement of local populations in those projects could put a spanner in those plans.

Energy Cooperation as a Catalyst for Development

According to (Xie et al. 2022), energy cooperation is the most relevant aspect of CPEC in eradicating the energy poverty, which hampers economic and social development in the Pakistan. It indicates experience in successful implementations such as the Sahiwal power plant where along with energy availability has been addressed, so has employment opportunities and human capital development. However, the authors highlight the following concerns that are contrary to Pakistan's renewable energy initiatives that include political instability, promoter associated financial issues and coal-based energy. They demand a better sociopolitical approach to generally promoting energy commerce for the mutual fostering of socio-economic value.

Social and Financial Dimensions of Poverty Alleviation

(Ashraf, 2017) gives a good understanding of poverty situation in Pakistan with a focus on rural-urban divide, gender and socio-economic disparities. The failure of the government, particularly the programs such as the Benazir Income Support Program (BISP) is also decried and impacts of the cut including a call for research based, effective, multi-dimensional anti-poverty and gender sensitive initiatives is discussed and how these do not capture the regional variation of poverty or empower poor women. (Zubair and Hayat, 2020) have reviewed the literature on the impact of financial sector development on poverty reduction and have realized the existence of a feedback loop where demand is also increased with financial inclusion once more promoting financial sector development. They recommend changes that would help correct the market failures such as high lending charges and information failure in a bid to foster equal financial development as well as sustainable poverty reduction.

Insights from China's Unprecedented Success

A concrete analysis of China's successful experience in eradicating extreme poverty is given by (Akram, 2022). Indeed, the study found out that political leadership in the country is strong and that the interventions have been focused and consistent with the principles of inclusive growth that values human beings. These development indicators including infrastructural development in the rural areas, health and education, have revolutionized the social and economic fabrics which can be seen as useful tips for developing countries including Pakistan. (Wang et al., 2024) have discussed the paired assistance model in China, which is the combination of governmental strategies and societal resources to fight poverty in an efficient manner. They emphasize the effectiveness and local sources mobilization together with the private companies and economic independence, as well as an approach to the specific local context. Therefore, the study establishes the need for collaborative governance if sustainable poverty reduction strategies are to be developed and implemented.

Targeted Interventions and Health Outcomes

(Guo et al., 2019) recommend that future efforts for poverty reduction should take into account the context and adoption of technology in the poverty alleviation strategies like the ones employed in China. These programs show how organizations need to attain integrated funding and involve the public for enhanced openness and fairness. (Tariq et al. 2021) consider poverty in Pakistan concerning POSS, BISP, and the Sehat Sahulat Program (SSP). Whereas, BISP is responsible for meeting necessities on the basis of income, SSP aims at meeting necessities in the sphere of health which contributes to human development. The above study therefore recommends the incorporation of these programs in the general poverty reduction framework for the purpose of enduring development.

The functions of poverty in one or more dimensions are described accompanied with the relationship between governance, education, infrastructure, trade and socio economics policies. It is possible to conclude that the experience, which China has had during its development, especially its focus on institutional changes, selective state interventions, and the inclusion of growth, is useful for understanding the conditions for Pakistan. The nations should adapt specific, context-related solutions and try to build the cooperation with other governments and social forces that way poverty may be tackled comprehensively and people can start the pathways into the sustainable development.

Key Takeaways From Literature

A) Similarities between Pakistan and China

1. Early similarities: In the late 1970s, Pakistan and China experienced similar levels of poverty.
2. Economic Growth: Both nations have experienced economic growth, but China demonstrated a higher and more stable rate of growth and sustainability.

3. Reduction in Poverty: Alleviating poverty was an objective for both countries, and for China these approaches have been thoroughly executed.

B) Variations between China and Pakistan

Key Insights for Pakistan

1. Strategies for Alleviating Poverty - China's methods for combating poverty have been more focused and effective, emphasizing the significance of economic development, healthcare, and education. On the other hand, Pakistan's strategies have been more scattered and less effective.
2. Institutional Capacity - China possesses a more effective and efficient government along with enhanced institutional capacity, enabling it to implement its poverty reduction policies more successfully. The government of Pakistan is more corrupt and inefficient, and its institutional capacity is less robust.
3. Economic Development - With an increased focus on industrialization and urbanization, China has experienced more rapid and sustained economic growth. Pakistan's economy has experienced slower and more unequal growth.

C) China's Approaches to Alleviate Poverty

1. Economic Growth - China's initiatives to fight poverty have mainly focused on economic growth, especially urbanization and industrial growth.
2. Education and Healthcare - China has invested heavily in the education and healthcare sectors, which are crucial for economic development and the battle against poverty.
3. Focused Poverty Alleviation - China has implemented strategies aimed at poverty reduction that are specifically designed for certain demographic groups and regions.

D) Role of CPEC in Poverty Alleviation in Pakistan

1. Economic Growth and Poverty Reduction - CPEC is a huge initiative, and infrastructure development will lead it, which is one of the basic needs for economic growth and poverty alleviation.
2. (Poverty Reduction Effects of CPEC) Industrialization and Urbanization - The potential of CPEC is to promote industrialization and urbanization in Pakistan which can mitigate poverty.
3. Job creation - CPEC generates jobs in Pakistan which can help alleviate poverty.

E) Challenges and Limitations

1. Limited Institutional Capacity - Traditional poverty alleviation methods may not be effective due to Pakistan's unique context. The government has limited institutional capacity to implement welfare initiatives, and bureaucracy in this regard can be challenging.
2. Corruption - Corruption is a persistent issue in Pakistan that can hinder poverty alleviation efforts.
3. Security Issues - Single of the issues which offer obstacle in the route of poverty minimization strategies is that of protection in Pakistan.

Methodology

This research utilizes a qualitative, comparative analysis method to explore the poverty reduction strategies of China and Pakistan, emphasizing the impact of the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC). An extensive examination of academic articles, reports, and books released from 2010 to 2024 was carried out utilizing peer-reviewed and reliable sources. Important search phrases consisted of “poverty reduction in China,” “strategies for reducing poverty in Pakistan,” and “CPEC and socio-economic progress.” The study employs a comparative framework to investigate the economic, social, and institutional elements that aid in poverty reduction, focusing on the impacts of industrialization, urbanization, education, healthcare, and governance reforms. Thematic analysis was utilized to recognize trends, including the effects of infrastructure development under CPEC and the efficacy of targeted interventions in both nations. Special focus was placed on the impact of CPEC on poverty alleviation in Pakistan, highlighting its possible advantages and related obstacles. Moreover, an analysis of policies was carried out to evaluate Pakistan's initiatives for poverty alleviation, including the Benazir Income Support Program (BISP) and the Sehat Sahulat Program (SSP), informed by insights gained from China's effective approaches. Studies of China's Special Economic Zones (SEZs) and CPEC initiatives in Pakistan were analyzed to grasp practical execution and results. Although the research utilizes secondary data, it offers essential insights into the socio-economic elements and policy measures required for successful poverty reduction in Pakistan.

Result and Conclusion

The findings from the studies analyzed show that reducing poverty in Pakistan is a complicated matter that necessitates a diverse strategy. The literature indicates that education, economic growth, and infrastructure improvement are essential elements in alleviating poverty. The China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) is viewed as a transformative initiative for enhancing economic growth and alleviating poverty in Pakistan. Nevertheless, the research also emphasizes the importance of tackling concerns like governance, institutional capability, and social inequality to guarantee that the advantages of CPEC are distributed fairly among all parts of the population. The results from the studies examined also highlight the significance of focused interventions, like the Benazir Income Support Program (BISP) and the Sehat Sahulat Program (SSP), in tackling poverty and enhancing health results. Research indicates that these initiatives have successfully decreased consumption-based poverty and improved healthcare access, yet it is essential to incorporate them into wider strategies to guarantee sustainability and better results.

Additionally, the examined studies emphasize the necessity of tackling regional disparities and inequalities within Pakistan. The literature indicates that the western regions of Balochistan and Khyber Pakhtunkhwa are falling short in economic growth and poverty alleviation, necessitating focused efforts to tackle these inequalities.

To sum up, the research analyzed indicates that alleviating poverty in Pakistan necessitates a holistic strategy that tackles economic growth, education, infrastructure improvement, governance, institutional capability, and social disparities. The CPEC can foster economic growth and alleviate poverty, but its advantages must be distributed fairly among all groups within the population. Targeted programs like BISP and SSP can effectively tackle poverty and enhance health results, but they must be incorporated into wider strategies for sustainability and improved outcomes. Tackling regional disparities and inequalities is essential for fostering inclusive growth and reducing poverty in Pakistan.

Recommendations

A comprehensive approach is required to handle the intricate problem of poverty reduction in Pakistan. This entails putting into practice a comprehensive plan that tackles social inequality, governance, infrastructural development, economic growth, education, and institutional capacity. Targeted initiatives must concentrate on areas like Balochistan and Khyber Pakhtunkhwa that are falling behind in terms of economic growth and poverty alleviation. Poverty reduction and economic growth may also be achieved by utilizing the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor's (CPEC) full potential. Furthermore, it is essential to invest in the development of infrastructure, such as networks for communication, electricity, and transportation.

It's also critical to guarantee that everyone has access to high-quality education, especially in underserved and rural regions. Health outcomes can also be enhanced by increasing access to healthcare services, especially via focused initiatives like the Sehat Sahulat Program (SSP). For poverty reduction measures to be implemented effectively, institutions must be strengthened and good governance practices—such as accountability, openness, and participation—must be encouraged. Poverty and inequality can be addressed by putting social security programs like the Benazir Income Support Program (BISP) into place and growing them. Last but not least, putting in place a strong monitoring and assessment system may assist in tracking developments and making necessary strategy adjustments.

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